

DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

*Khamidova Kamilla Ulugbekovna,
undergraduate student of Namangan
Institute of Engineering and Technology,
Republic of Uzbekistan, Namangan
hamidovakamilla1@gmail.com*

Abstract: This article discusses the main socio-economic prospects that open up for the Republic of Uzbekistan due to the introduction of the digital economy, as well as the problems of digital infrastructure that require immediate solutions.

Keywords: digital economics, digitalization, infrastructure, digital, ICT, infrastructure.

Today, at the global level, a relatively new direction of the economic structure, the digital economy, is gaining more and more relevance. The prerequisites for this are:

- firstly, the scientific and technological revolution that began in the middle of the previous century, which served as a powerful impetus for giving intellectual capital a central link in the field of science and in the subsequent transition from the industrial way of society to the post-industrial one;
- introduction of automated systems into circulation, both in production and at the stage of distribution of goods and services;
- the gradual introduction of artificial intelligence in the vast majority of areas of public life;
- development and expansion of the virtual space;

- the gradual digitization of big data in order to facilitate work, improve the quality of life and the transition of the economies of countries to a relatively high level of development. Scientist Gorchikova I.N. in her work noted the need to create automated systems: “the amount of information that needs to be processed is so great that it has long exceeded human capabilities”[1].

For the first time the term “digital economy” was introduced into circulation in 1995 by the American scientist Nicholas Negreonte in his work “Being Digital” [2]. To date, modern economists, scientists and politicians have given a huge number of interpretations of the concept of the digital economy, the most capacious of which, in our opinion, are the following: “The digital economy is an economy in which, due to the development of digital technologies, there is an increase in labor productivity, the competitiveness of companies, reducing production costs, creating new jobs, a noticeable decrease in the level of poverty and social inequality”[3]. Also, the Canadian scientist Don Tapscott, in his book “Electronic-Digital Society: Pros and Cons of the Age of Network Intelligence”, describing the features of developed countries, noted the digital form of representing objects, the impact of information technology on business, the public administration system and gave the digital economy the following definition: “economy based on the use of information computer technologies” [4].

In other words, the digital economy implies activities for the production, exchange, distribution and consumption of goods and services, carried out through the use of advanced technologies, the main objectives of which are:

- increase in labor productivity;
- reduction of monotonous physical labor due to the introduction of artificial intelligence;
- increasing the level of well-being by improving the quality of goods and services produced and provided using digital technologies;

- continuous management of a large amount of information, including the collection, storage, processing and analysis, as well as free access to it;
- reducing the cost of production and distribution of goods and services;
- increasing the literacy of the population and providing opportunities for quick and high-quality retraining of personnel;
- integration of international relations and reaching a new level with subsequent positive development dynamics for developing and developed countries;
- creation of a competitive environment at the micro and macro levels;
- development of long-term forecasting of the behavior of the economy and minimization of the risks of economic stagnation.

It is also important that due to digitalization, data becomes open, and the financial activities of both small businesses and private entrepreneurship, as well as larger state and non-state institutions, become more transparent, reducing the possibility of various fraud, fraud and corruption.

It is apparent that the advent of the digital economy has opened up enormous opportunities for any country that can significantly alter and enhance human life. But is it as easy as it seems at first glance, and what is necessary for the full functioning of the modern system, which is the imperative of the times? In order to understand these issues, it is necessary to analyze all the components of the digital economy. In 2001, the American scientist Thomas Mezenburg singled out 3 main components that can be statistically evaluated and measured [5]. The main link among them is the supporting infrastructure, which includes networks, telecommunications, hardware, artificial intelligence, big data processing centers and much more. The next link is electronic business, that is, the conduct of any business process through the use of computer technology, as well as electronic commerce - the sale of goods and services using the Internet. Any digital process cannot be carried out without the necessary level of development of the

infrastructure tuned for it, which in our case is the network. Moreover, it is worth noting that it is necessary to constantly develop and modernize the infrastructure based on scientific development.

Based on the requirements, the digital infrastructure can also be segmented into numerous key parts depending on the requirements. Of course, the first component is the network and communication. With the timely development of physical infrastructure, not only for small businesses and private entrepreneurship, but also for the state as a whole, a huge range of opportunities is revealed, such as:

- an easier way to increase the client base not only in the domestic market, but also in the external one;
- attracting investments, which in itself is beneficial for any business;
- establishing trade, economic and political relations with foreign countries and much more.

In this regard, at present, the Republic of Uzbekistan has seen an active expansion of the mobile communication network and a general increase in the involvement of an increasing number of areas in the Internet. Table 1 shows the statistics of changes in the total number of people provided with constant access to the Internet in the Republic of Uzbekistan over the past 10 years [6]. The statistics makes it clear that there is a slow but steady progression in this direction, but this is not the end and there is no purpose in stopping there.

Table 1.

Number of subscribers provided with the Internet (for every 100 people)

Years	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Number of subscribers	23	25	31	26	27	30	34	41	42	50	54

The second and no less important link is the development of ICT, which is

a kind of framework on which the entire digital infrastructure rests. To date, the Republic of Uzbekistan has already taken a number of measures to accelerate the formation of a digital economy. So, during 2020-2022 it is planned to attract 678.6 million dollars of investments in the field of ICT and communications, see Table 2[7].

Table 2.

Attracting investments in the field of Information and Communication Technologies in the Republic of Uzbekistan (mln USD)

Years	Total investment amount	Direct foreign investments	Foreign loans with state backing
2020	178,7	139,2	37,5
2021	241,7	171,9	67,7
2022	256,4	180,1	73,1

So what aspects of digital transformation do we need to pay attention to? The following are the main tasks that the state must complete:

- increase in funding for the introduction and development of information and communication technologies;
- improvement and continuous support of uninterrupted Internet connection not only in large business centers, but also in the most remote corners of the country;
- ensuring legal and technical security;
- expansion of existing infrastructure;

- creating conditions for the development of digital literacy by the population, training highly qualified personnel taking into account modern requirements on a long-term basis, as well as creating conditions for their rapid retraining.

List of references

1. Gerchikova I.N. The process of making and implementing management decisions // Management in Russia and abroad. 2003. №12. pp. 39-42.
2. Negroponte, N. // BEING DIGITAL. Knopf. Paperback edition, 1996.
3. World Bank. Digital dividends.
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/23347/210671RuSum.pdf>
4. Tapscott, Don. Electronic-digital society: Pros and cons of the era of network intelligence / Translated from eng. Igor Dubinsky. Ed. Sergei Pisarev. //Kyiv. – INT Press; Moscow. - Relph book.-1999.-432 – p.
5. Golovenchik, G. G. Digital economy [Electronic resource]: textbook-method. complex / G. G. Golovenchik. - Minsk: BGU, 2020. 12 – pp.
6. The number of subscribers provided with the Internet per 100 people (in units), State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics.
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2020 “On measures to implement the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2022”.
8. Хамидова, Камилла Улугбековна. "ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЧЕТВЕРТОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ РЕВОЛЮЦИИ" Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, vol. 2, no. 4, 2022, pp. 595-597.